

Removal of Malachite Green from aqueous solution by Kodo (*Paspalum serobiculatum* Linn.) husk : Kinetic study and equilibrium isotherm analysis

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Abstract : Present study deals with the utility of an agricultural waste, Kodo husk, as an adsorbent in removal of dye, Malachite Green (MG). Surface study of Untreated Kodo Husk was done using Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. Batch adsorption process was used to determine the adsorption characteristics of MG onto Untreated Kodo Husk (UKH). Which include the study of adsorption with respect to the changes in initial pH of dye solutions, contact time, initial dye concentration, adsorbent dose and temperature. The dye adsorption equilibrium was attained for MG in 120 min of contact time. The adsorption kinetic pseudo-first order, pseudo-second order and intra-particle diffusion models, were selected to follow the adsorption process. It was shown that the adsorption data were well described by the pseudo-second order model. The equilibrium data were interpreted in terms of the Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm models. Adsorption of MG on to UKH followed the Langmuir isotherm. The mono layer adsorption capacity of UKH was found to be 71.42 mg/g using the Langmuir equation. The determination of thermodynamic parameters established that the adsorption process was feasible, spontaneous and endothermic in nature in the temperature range of 303–327 °C.

Keywords : Adsorption isotherm equilibrium, kinetics, Kodo husk, Malachite Green, thermodynamics.

Introduction

Dyes are widely used in many industries such as textile, fiber, cosmetic, pharmaceutical, leather, paper, plastic, printing and food to color. About 10000 different dyes are annually used in various industrial processes¹. A large amount of dyes are discharged to the wastewater effluent annually which severely pollute the water body and damage the aquatic life by increasing the COD, BOD and suspended solid of the water body. Color interferes with penetration of sun light into water, retards photosynthesis, inhibits the growth of aquatic biota and interferes with the gas solubility of water bodies².

The release of dyes into the environment is of further concern due to their toxic, mutagenic and carcinogenic characteristics^{3–5}. Even a trace amount of dye present in the aquatic system may cause severe health problem to mankind as well as to animals. Malachite Green (MG) has a complicated chemical structure (Fig. 1). It is resilient to fading on exposure to light and water and is therefore difficult to be removed from waste water. MG when discharged into water it will affect the aquatic life and

Fig. 1. Structure of Malachite Green.

cause detrimental effects in liver, gill, kidney, intestine, gonads and pituitary gonadotrophic cell⁶. Studies also confirm that the products formed after the degradation of MG are also not safe and have carcinogenic potential^{7,8}. Thus it becomes necessary to remove such a toxic dye from waste water before it is released into aquatic environment.

There are many chemical and physical methods such as flocculation, electro-floatation, precipitation, coagulation, ion exchange, membrane filtration, electro chemical destruction, irradiation, ozonation, and katox treatment method that have been used to treat the wastewater

having dyes⁹ but these processes are costly and can't be used effectively to treat a large quantity of dyes. However, adsorption is most suitable method for solving this type of problem. Several agro-industrial wastes/byproducts have been used for the adsorption of dyes.

To date, adsorbent such as neem saw dust¹⁰, rattan sawdust¹¹, orange peel¹², coffee bean¹³, oil palm trunk fiber¹⁴, deoiled soya cake⁴, bagasse fly ash¹⁵, sugar cane dust¹⁶, potato plant waste¹⁷, prosopis cineraria¹⁸ and banana pseudostem fiber¹⁹ etc. have been used for the removal of MG.

In this work, we attempt to utilize untreated Kodo (*Paspalum serobiculatum* Linn.) husk, an agriculture waste of family Eurotiaceae, for the first time. It is a commonly grown cereal in the hilly area of north India mainly in Uttarakhand, the seeds of this plant are in use for forming flour as an alternative of wheat flour after grinding. Its husk is a by-product that is used as fodder in a small amount and its maximum part is a waste for the people there, so they used to burnt the husk to dispose the material, instead of burning, this agricultural waste material can be successfully exploit as a low cost material for the removal of dyes or other water pollutants. Therefore, its use as an adsorbent can also save the environment from the pollution due to burning of Kodo husk. The advantage of treating wastewater by untreated solid biological waste is low price and easy to regenerate which decrease the treatment cost of wastewater.

Results and discussion

Characterizations of UKH :

The FTIR technique is an important tool to identify the functional groups, which are capable of adsorbing dyes. FTIR spectra of UKH, before and after adsorption of MG were shown in Fig. 2. Spectral band observed at 2962–2853 cm^{-1} and 1470–1375 cm^{-1} represent C–H stretching and C–H bending group. The peak at 1725 cm^{-1} corresponds to C=O group. Carbonyl stretching vibration at 1725–1700 cm^{-1} , carboxylate ion stretching in 1610–1550 cm^{-1} region shows presence of carboxylic acid. IR spectra also represent aldehyde group as it shows carbonyl stretching vibration 1740–1695 cm^{-1} . Peak at 1620–1510 cm^{-1} is due to N–H bending vibration. Peaks at 900–1100 cm^{-1} and 700–900 cm^{-1} represents $\text{CH}_2\text{-O-Si}$ and Si-C group respectively. Characteristic change were observed in the FTIR spectrum of UKH after adsorption of MG dye on its surface.

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of UKH and MKH.

The result indicated that some peaks were shifted or disappeared, and new peaks were also detected. These changes in the spectrum indicated the possible involvement of those functional groups on the surface of the UKH in the adsorption process.

Determination of pH_{pzc} of UKH :

The point of zero charge of an adsorbent determination is very important characteristic that determine the pH at which the adsorbent surface has net electrical neutrality²⁰. To find out pH_{pzc} , the experiments were conducted at different pH ranging from 2–11, by adding 0.1 g of adsorbent to 50 mg/L of 0.1 M solution KNO_3 and shake it for 2 h in an orbital shaker. The pH of the solution was measured after 2 h shaking. Values of pH initial – pH final, was plotted against pH initial (Fig. 3), from the graph we can say that the pH_{pzc} of UKH was 8. At solution when $\text{pH} > \text{pH}_{\text{pzc}}$, the adsorbent surface negatively charged and favors uptake of cationic dye due to increase electrostatic force of attraction. At $\text{pH} < \text{pH}_{\text{pzc}}$, the surface becomes positively charged, concentration of H^+ were high and they compete with positively charged cationic dye, Malachite Green. Thus MG adsorption onto UKH is favored at pH higher than pH_{pzc} . It was found that % removal of MG was less at low pH and high at high pH.

Effect of contact time and initial dye concentration :

The removal of Malachite Green dye onto UKH at 303 \pm 2 K is shown in Fig. 4. It was found that removal of MG gradually increases with the increase in contact

Fig. 3. Plot of $(pH_f - pH_i)$ vs pH_i .

Fig. 4. Effect of contact time for adsorption of Malachite Green at different initial concentration using UKH.

time and attends equilibrium after 120 min. At low initial concentration of dye, the removal is very fast, and higher removal of MG is obtained. Fig. 4 also shows that rate of adsorption of the dye was very fast during initial stage of adsorption process. The concentration gradient will be responsible for these changes in a rate of adsorption. In the beginning, because of high concentration gradient, the driving force helps in this rapid adsorption. However, as the concentration gradient decreases with time, the rate was reduced till the equilibrium is attended and therefore, after the equilibrium time and a particular time interval adsorption percentage remains almost constant.

At 250 mg/L of initial dye concentration, 52.2% of MG was removed by 0.1 g of UKH adsorbent at $pH \sim 7$

whereas at 50 mg/L of initial dye concentration it becomes 90.76% for MG.

However an increase in initial concentration of dye solution enhances the net adsorption uptake of dye. This is so because the initial dye concentrations provide the driving force to overcome the resistance to the mass transfer of the dye between the aqueous and the solid phase. The increase in initial concentration also enhances the interaction between adsorbent and dye. For constant dose of adsorbent (UKH), at high initial dye concentration, the available adsorption site become fewer and hence the removal of BG depends upon initial dye concentration.

Effect of hydrogen ion concentration :

The surface charge of the solid phase (UKH) could be modified by changing the pH of the solution, so pH plays an important role in the removal of ion by the adsorption process. Fig. 5 shows that the effect of pH on the adsorption of Malachite Green. It can be seen that the removal of malachite green gradually increase with increase in pH

Fig. 5. Effect of pH for the removal of Malachite Green dyes onto UKH adsorbent.

up to pH 8 (99% removal). Since, maximum removal showed at the pH 8 but as we consider the natural water body it's hard to maintain the pH at 8 and high pH also change the structural stability so all the experiments were carried at natural pH 7.

While at the pH more than 10 MG solutions become colorless without adsorbent. pK_a value of MG is 10.3 so, at the pH higher then this value the dye is in its dissociated form that change the color of the solution. So the

experiment performed at the pH below 10.3 in which the predominant species was MGOOCCOOH . Same result found by Mall *et al.*²¹. Studied the effect of initial pH on the blank solution of MG without adsorbent. It gets protonated in the acidic medium and deprotonated in the higher pH²².

The low pH is unfavorable for MG adsorption on UKH. Acidic medium of the test solution decrease the negatively charged adsorption site which did not favors the adsorption of positively charged cationic dye due to electronic repulsion and also due to presence of H^+ ion of the solution, competing with dye cations for the adsorption.

Effect of adsorbent dose :

Study of the effect of adsorbent dose gives an idea about the effectiveness of the adsorbent. It was found that with the increase in adsorbent dose from 0.05–0.2 g the percentage removal also increases. It increases from 74.7% to 95.53% (Fig. 6). These adsorbent dose experiments were carried out in the pH 8, concentration 50 mg/L and agitation time 120 min, at 100 rpm. The increase the percentage of dye removal with increasing adsorbent dose is due to increase of sorption active sites at the adsorbent surface with increasing the dose.

Fig. 6. Effect of adsorbent dose on % removal of Malachite Green by UKH.

Adsorption equilibrium isotherm :

The results of experimental were analyzed using Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm models, as it is important to find best fit isotherm to evaluate the efficiency

of prepared adsorbent to develop suitable industrial adsorption system designs.

Langmuir isotherm :

The Langmuir isotherms model predicts the existence of monolayer coverage of the sorbates such that when an adsorption site on the adsorbent surface is occupied by a sorbate, no further sorption can takes place at this site. The model is based on assumption that adsorption takes place at specific homogeneous sites within the adsorbent and there is no interaction between the adsorbed species. The model has the following form²² :

$$q_e = q_m K_L C_e / 1 + K_L C_e \tag{1}$$

Linear form of this expression is

$$C_e/q_e = 1/q_m K_L + C_e/q_m \tag{2}$$

where, q_e (mg/g) and C_e (mg/L) are the amount of adsorbed adsorbate per unit weight of adsorbent and adsorbed adsorbate concentration in solution in equilibrium, respectively. The constant K_L (L/mg) is the Langmuir equilibrium constant and the K_L/q_m gives the theoretical monolayer saturation capacity, q_m . Therefore a plot of C_e/q_e versus C_e gives a straight line of slope $1/q_m$ and intercepts $1/q_m K_L$.

The essential factor of Langmuir isotherm can be expressed in term of a dimensionless constant called separation factor (R_L , also called equilibrium parameter) which is defined by the following equation :

$$R_L = 1/1 + K_L C_o \tag{3}$$

where C_o (mg/L) is the initial adsorbate concentration and q_m (mg/g) is the Langmuir constant related to the energy of adsorption. The value of R_L indicates the shape of the isotherm to be either unfavorable ($R_L > 1$). Linear ($R_L = 1$). Favorable ($0 < R_L < 1$) or irreversible ($R_L = 0$) (Fig. 7).

Freundlich isotherm :

The Freundlich isotherm can be applied to non ideal adsorption on heterogeneous surface of different adsorption energies as well as multilayer sorption and is expressed by the following equation²² :

$$q_e = K_F C_e^{1/n} \tag{4}$$

A linear form of this expression is

$$\log q_e = \log K_F + 1/n \cdot \log C_e \tag{5}$$

where K_F ($\text{mg}^{1-1/n} \text{L}^{1/n} \text{g}^{-1}$) is the Freundlich constant

Fig. 7. Comparison of equilibrium isotherm : (a) Langmuir plot, (b) Freundlich plot.

and n is the Freundlich exponent. Therefore a plot of $\log q_e$ versus $\log C_e$ enables the constant and exponent n to be determined.

In this work in addition to Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm, the models were also evaluated by average relative error function²³, which measures the differences of the amount of dye uptake by the adsorbent predicted by the models and the actual q measured experimentally.

Average relative error =

$$100\%/n \sum_i^n (q_{cal} - q_{exp})/q_{exp} \quad (6)$$

where, q_{cal} is each value of q predicted by the fitted model and q_{exp} is the each value of q measured experimentally and n is the number of experiment performed.

The adsorption isotherm is important for the description of how the adsorbate will interact with the adsorbent

and give the idea about the adsorption capacity of the adsorbate. The adsorption equilibrium data were analyzed by Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm model equations. All the isotherm constant and correlation coefficient are given in Table 2 and the adsorption isotherm plots are given in Fig. 7. The adsorption capacity of UKH was found to be 71.42 mg/g for MG by using the Langmuir model equation. The adsorption capacity of UKH was compared with the adsorption capacity of other adsorbents of the literature and the comparative data are given in Table 3. In most cases the adsorption capacity of UKH is found to be better than many other adsorbents reported in the literature. The value of R_L fell in the range from

Table 1. EDX analysis of UKH

Elements	Wt%	At%
C	64.24	73.81
O	25.41	21.92
Mg	0.56	0.32
Si	3.04	1.49
P	1.27	0.57
K	0.89	0.32

Table 2. Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm parameters for the adsorption of MG on UKH

	Malachite Green
Langmuir isotherm :	
q_{max} (mg/g)	71.42
K_L (L/mg)	0.1
R^2	0.998
Average relative error (%)	16
Freundlich isotherm :	
K_F (mg/g)	15.17
n	3.021
R^2	0.937
Average relative error (%)	12.7

Table 3. Adsorption capacities of MG on various adsorbents

Dyes	Adsorbents	Adsorption capacities (mg/g)	References
Malachite Green	UKH	71.42	Present study
Malachite Green	Oil palm trunk fiber	149.35	14
Malachite Green	Banana pseudo stem fiber	26.5	19
Malachite Green	Potato leaf	33.33	17
Malachite Green	Neem saw dust	4.3	10
Malachite Green	Potato stem	27	17
Malachite Green	Sugarcane dust	4.88	16

0.16–0.038 for MG, between 50–250 mg/L of initial dye concentrating, indicating that the MG adsorption onto UKH is favorable under the studied conditions. The Freundlich isotherm constant n , gives an idea for the favorability of the adsorption process. The value of n should be less than 10 and higher than unity for favorable adsorption condition. As can be seen from Table 2, the value of n for MG was in the range of 1–10, indicating that adsorption is a favorable process. By the comparing correlation coefficient values obtained from the Langmuir and Freundlich model. It can be concluded that Langmuir isotherm model is more suitable for MG in comparison to Freundlich isotherm model.

However, Freundlich model shows low average relative error. The average relative error measured how close the q fitted by the model to the actual q measured experimentally. The correlation coefficient values of Freundlich isotherm is also good, this may be due to both heterogeneous and homogeneous distribution of active sites on the surface of the UKH.

Kinetics study :

In order to investigate the mechanism of adsorption and to determine the rate controlling step the following kinetic rate equations have been used to test the experimental data.

Pseudo-first order equation :

The pseudo-first order equation of Lagergren is generally expressed as follows²² :

$$dq_t/dt = k_1 (q_e - q_t) \tag{7}$$

After integrating and applying boundary condition, $t = 0$ to $t = t$ and $q_t = 0$ to $q_t = q_t$; then integration form of eq. (8) becomes

$$q_t = q_e (1 - e^{-k_1 t}) \tag{8}$$

However, eq. (9) is transformed into its linear form for use in kinetic analysis of data as

$$\ln (q_e - q_t) = \ln q_e - k_1 t \tag{9}$$

where, q_e (mg/g) and q_t (mg/g) are the amount of adsorbed adsorbate at equilibrium and at time t , respectively, and k_1 (min^{-1}) is the rate constant of pseudo-first order adsorption.

Pseudo-second order equation :

If the rate of adsorption has second-order mechanism, the pseudo-second order chemisorptions kinetic rate equation is expressed as follows²² :

$$dq_t/dt = k_2 (q_e - q_t)^2 \tag{10}$$

Integrating this equation for the boundary condition, gives

$$1/(q_e - q_t) = 1/q_e + k_2 t \tag{11}$$

which is integrated rate law for pseudo second order reaction eq. (12) can be rearrange to its linear form as

$$t/q_t = 1/k_2 q_e^2 + 1/q_e t \tag{12}$$

where, k_2 (g/mg min) is the equilibrium rate constant of pseudo-second order adsorption. If the pseudo-second order is applicable, the plot of t/q_e against t should give a linear relationship, from which q_e and k_2 can be determined from the slope and intercept of the plot, and there is no need to know any parameter beforehand.

The results of the experiments were described by the obtained equilibrium parameters and error functions (R^2 and SSE) are listed in Table 4. The sum of the squares of the errors (SSE) was determined from the following equation :

$$SSE = \sum_{i=1}^p (q_e^{calc} - q_e^{exp})_i^2 \tag{13}$$

The adsorption kinetics of MG on UKH was studied. We

Table 4. Kinetic model parameters for adsorption of MG and GR on UKH

C_o (mg/L)	$q_{e,exp}$ (mg/g)	MG						
		Pseudo-first order			Pseudo-second order			
		K_1 (min^{-1})	$q_{e,cal}$ (mg/g)	R^2	K_2 (min^{-1})	$q_{e,cal}$ (mg/g)	R^2	
50	23.94	0.016	1.5	0.83	0.053	23.26	0.999	
100	46.37	0.044	29.1	0.928	0.006	45.45	0.998	
150	66.98	0.021	13.24	0.998	0.008	58.82	1	
200	82.14	0.016	14.42	0.946	0.004	71.43	1	
250	94	0.020	12.85	0.905	0.006	71.43	0.999	

compared the q_e experimental value with the value of q_e calculated of pseudo-first order equation and found that they varied a lot, whereas, in case of pseudo-second order equation the calculated q_e value are much closer to the experimental q_e value (Table 4). From the Table 4 it is clear that the value of regression correlation coefficient R^2 are more close to 1 in case of pseudo-second order equation in comparison to pseudo-first order equation while the *SSE* error functions adopted advantageously low values for pseudo-second order equation (102.39) and very high for pseudo-first order equation (6427.64). From Table 4, it is also revealed that the values of rate constant, k_2 decreases with increasing initial dye concentration. The reason for this behavior may be due to the lower competition for the sorption site at lower concentration. At higher concentration the competition for the active surface sites will be high so the lower sorption rates are obtained. Hence it can be concluded that the adsorption kinetics of BG is describe pseudo-second order chemical reaction.

Intra-particle diffusion study :

The possibility of intra-particle diffusion resistance affecting adsorption was explored by using the intra-particle diffusion model as²⁴ :

$$q_t = k_{id} t^{1/2} + C \quad (14)$$

where, k_{id} is the intra-particle diffusion rate constant C gives the information regarding the thickness of boundary layer. According to this model, the plot between q_t versus $t^{1/2}$ should be linear if intra-particle diffusion is involved in the adsorption process, and if these line passes through the origin, then intra-particle diffusion is the rate controlling step. When the plot doesn't passes though the origin as shown in Fig. 9, this is indicative of some degree of boundary layer control, and this further shows that intra-particle is not only the rate controlling step, but also other kinetic model may control the rate of adsorption of dye (Malachite Green) onto UKH. The values of intercept listed in Table 4 and give an idea about the boundary layer (film diffusion) thickness, such as the large is the intercept, the greater is the boundary layer effect.

Thermodynamic study :

The Gibbs free energy change of the adsorption process is related to the equilibrium constant by the classic Van't Hoff equation :

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K \quad (15)$$

Fig. 8. Pseudo-second order reaction for Malachite Green.

Fig. 9. Intra-particle diffusion plots for adsorption of MG on UKH.

where, ΔG° is free energy change (kJ mol^{-1}), T is the absolute temperature (K), R is universal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) and K is the Langmuir constant. According to thermodynamics, the Gibbs free energy change is also related to the entropy change and heat of adsorption at constant temperature by the following equation :

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad (16)$$

Combining above two equations, we get

$$\ln K = \Delta G^\circ/RT = \Delta S^\circ/R - \Delta H^\circ/RT \quad (17)$$

where ΔG° is the free energy change (kJ mol^{-1}), ΔH° the change in enthalpy (kJ mol^{-1}), ΔS° the entropy change ($\text{kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), T the absolute temperature (K) and R the universal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$). Thus ΔH° can be determined by the slope of the linear Van't Hoff plot, i.e. as $\ln K$ versus $(1/T)^{25}$ (Fig. 10).

Fig. 10. Van't Hoff plot for the adsorption of Malachite Green dye onto UKH.

The thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of MG is given in Table 6. Negative value of ΔG° shows that adsorption process is spontaneous. Change in enthalpy ΔH° is positive indicating that the process is endothermic and the positive value of ΔS° shows increased disorder at the solid solution interphase during the adsorption of the dye MG.

Table 5. Intra-particle diffusion parameters for adsorption of Malachite Green dyes onto UKH

Dye	Concentration (mg/L)	k_{id} (mg/g min ⁻¹)	C	R ²
Malachite Green	50	0.246	20.82	0.881
	100	1.874	28.62	0.928
	150	0.737	47.71	0.799
	200	1.228	52.94	0.777
	250	0.913	56.35	0.729

Table 6. Thermodynamic parameters adsorption of MG by UKH

	ΔG (J/mol)			ΔH (J/mol)	ΔS (J/mol-K)
	303 K	313 K	323 K		
Malachite Green	921.71	1114.66	1292.46	4450.48	17.73

Conclusion :

The adsorption method requires use of adsorbents which are low cost, easily available and possess high adsorption capacity. The present study shows the potential of untreated Kodo husk (UKH), which is an abundantly available agricultural waste mainly in Uttarakhand region, is an effective adsorbent for the removal of cationic dye

Malachite Green (MG) from aqueous solution. From the study we can conclude that the adsorbent is an agricultural waste so this waste represents unused resources and also present serious disposal problems. The UKH was used without any previous activation treatment which decreases the adsorption costs.

The adsorption characteristic of MG onto UKH was evaluated in terms of equilibrium, kinetics and thermodynamic parameters. The adsorption kinetics was predicted by pseudo-second order model and adsorption was controlled by chemisorptions process. Equilibrium adsorption data for MG on UKH was best represented by the Langmuir isotherm. As a result of thermodynamic evaluation of MG adsorption, negative ΔG value revealed that adsorption of MG onto UKH is spontaneous and thermodynamically feasible, the positive values of ΔH suggested that endothermic nature of adsorption and the positive value of ΔS indicated the increasing randomness at the solid/solution interface during the adsorption process.

Material and method :

Preparation of adsorbent :

The Kodo (*Paspalum serobiculatum* Linn.) husk was collected from Pauri Garhwal District of Uttarakhand, India. The husk was washed thoroughly by double distilled water to remove the dust and other impurities. It was firstly dried at room temperature and then 80 °C in dry air oven for 24 h, the dried husk was ground and sieved to desired mesh size 0.25 mm, the prepared sample was abbreviated as UKH (Untreated Kodo Husk) and was stored in an airtight container for further use. No chemical or physical treatment was applied prior to adsorption experiments.

Adsorbates :

All chemicals used were of analytical grade and were purchased from Merck. These were not purified prior to use. Malachite green oxalate dye (MG) is a cationic dye having molecular formula = $C_{52}H_{54}N_4O_{12}$, C.I. = 42000 and $\lambda_{max} = 618$ nm (Fig. 1). The stock solution of the dye was prepared in double distilled water of 500 mg/L concentration and the required concentration of working dye solution were prepared by appropriate dilutions of the stock solution.

Instrumentation :

UV/Vis spectrophotometer (Systronics 2202, India)

was used to determine the concentration of MG in solutions. The digital pH meter (Systronics 335, Ahmedabad, India) was used to maintain appropriate pH and FTIR spectrophotometer (ABB FTLA 2000, Hyderabad, India) were used for the characterization of the adsorbent UKH.

Batch experimental programme :

Adsorption studies were carried out by batch mode to obtain the rate and equilibrium data. The experiments were performed to observe the effect of important parameters like contact time, pH, initial dye concentration and effect of adsorbent dose on the removal of MG. All experiments were conducted at the temperature 303 ± 2 K. In each adsorption experiment, 50 mL of dye solution of known concentration at pH 7 was added to 0.1 g of UKH in 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask and the mixture was stirred in thermostatic orbital shaker (Shivam India Pvt. Ltd.) at 100 rpm. The samples were withdrawn from the shaker at the predetermined time intervals and the adsorbent were separated from the solutions using Whatman filter paper No. 42. Residual dye concentration was determined from absorbance values measured before and after treatment with UKH at wavelength 618 nm with the double beam UV/Vis spectrophotometer. Experiments were also carried out in the pH range 2–10, which was adjusted by using 0.1 N HCl or 0.1 N NaOH solutions, to find out the optimum pH for the removal of MG. In order to investigate the effect of temperature on the adsorption characteristics studies were also carried out at different temperatures, 303–323 K.

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